

Environmental Scan Summary

The following provides an overview of neighbourhood assets and potential barriers/gaps for older adults. The features were identified through a structured assessment in June 2019. As such, this summary should be viewed as an overview of key features observed rather than an exhaustive list.

The Durand neighbourhood gives off a typical downtown feel. There was a noticeable divide between income levels. The wealthy live an above average lifestyle – some of the most beautiful housing seen throughout all neighbourhood's surveyed. Houses were well kept and adorned with beautiful gardens. In contrast, there were many apartment buildings and retirement homes in the area. The neighbourhood appeared to have more younger adults in comparison to older adults. Many appeared to be Caucasian, however, Ethiopian and Asian restaurants were noted in the area.

Outdoor social gathering spaces included City Hall, the YMCA, Durand Park, First Ontario Centre and the Art Gallery of Hamilton. The YMCA Seniors Active Living Centres programs are well developed, showing attention to the needs of older adults. This recreational centre has programs including: The Active Learning Centre for 55+ seniors, Peer Connector Program, South Asian Punjabi Program, and Bones Plus classes. A Pride flag was also noted indicating inclusivity in the community.

Two main strengths for this neighbourhood were health care and transportation services. There were many health care facilities in Durand including health care clinics, dentistry, naturopathy, osteopathy, CARE Centre for Internationally Educated Nurses, and pharmacies. Buses were frequent including several express buses, buses to the Hamilton airport and the Hamilton GO Centre. Many bus shelters were also present. Bicycle lanes on the major roadways and accessible sidewalks were observed. A gap in this neighbourhood was the lack of grocery stores, other than some convenience stores and Shoppers Drug Mart. There were also no protective services, such as Police or Fire departments identified in Durand.

Map of services identified in Durand

Index of services in Durand

Map Number	Description
Education	
1	Central Public School
2	Metropolitan College
3	Michael G. Degroote School of Medicine
Fitness/Recreation	
4	Hamilton Conservatory for the Arts*
5	Main Hess Activity Club*
6	Ryerson Recreation Centre*
Food Sources	
7	Big Bee Food Mart Hunter
8	Durand Coffee
Health/Social Services	
9	Charlton Dentistry + Physiotherapy
10	De Benetti Dentistry Professionals
11	Dr. Brian Paul, Optometrist
12	G. Gall Hearing & Tinnitus Centre
13	Guardian Pharmacy
14	Hamilton Environmental Health
15	Hamilton Ontario Works Employment
16	Medical Arts Clinic
17	Pediatric Dentistry
18	Shoppers Drugmart Pharmacy
19	Southwest Family Health Centre
20	St. Joseph Hospital
21	The Career Foundation
22	Urban Healing Studio
23	Wilson Rehabilitation
24	YMCA Employment Centre
25	YMCA Hamilton-Seniors Active Living Centres*
Housing	
26	Bay 100 Apartments
27	Bold Towers

28	City Housing
29	Core Lofts
30	Durand Retirement Residence*
31	Durand Village
32	El Duque Apartments
33	Fontainebleau Apartments
34	Indwell - Caroline Apartments
35	Jackson Villa Apartments
36	Le Palais and Capital Terrace
37	Lido Tower Apartments - Skyline Living
38	Royal Place
Parks	
39	Durand Park
Religious Centres	
40	Central Presbyterian Church
41	First Hamilton Christian Reformed Church
42	MacNab Street Presbyterian Church
43	St. James Church
44	St. Paul's Presbyterian Church
Retail Stores	
45	Country Style
46	Daisy Mart
47	Kiki's Closets
48	Shoppers Drug Mart
49	TD Canada Trust Branch and ATM

*Programs Targeted Specifically at older adults

Environmental Scan Update, 2022

The neighbourhood's programs and services appeared consistent with those available for the community in the initial environmental scan completed in 2019. The initial environmental scan identified 52 relevant services across various categories; presently, 53 services have been identified though the distribution of services has varied across the two time points. Minor changes are seen in the number of services across service categories in stores and health/social services (Table 1). These changes can be attributed to services no longer being operational due to COVID-19-related closures and other operational status changes due to the COVID-19 pandemic (e.g., changes in management, location changes, etc.). For example, Children's Dental Healthcare, a pediatric dental service, has been permanently moved to Burlington. Similarly, Country Style, a franchise location of a chain of coffee shops, was permanently closed following the COVID-19 pandemic. In terms of newly identified services, Baltan Periodontics, who perform procedures including dental implants and tissue grafting, was identified, and categorized within health/social services. Similarly, Downtown Main Dental Office was newly identified and included within the health/social services category.

The COVID-19 pandemic had varying degrees of impact on service delivery within the community. More specifically, among all the identified services in 2022 the largest proportion remain open and serve the community in person. This is followed by services that are unclear in status due to lack of updated, publicly available information and/or inability to contact the services, and services that are provided through online options, as a result of public safety concerns. Services with unclear operational statuses (i.e., services categorized as "unclear status (with an attempt to contact)" in Table 1) require further follow-up in order to verify the status of their operation. Table 2 provides a detailed list of services within the Durand neighborhood and their current operational status (as impacted by the COVID-19 pandemic).

Moreover, as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic there were some changes in ownership, management, and name of services. For instance, Dr. Brian Paul's Optometrist Clinic is now owned and managed by Dr. Sheldon Salaba, who renamed

the service Advance Vision. Despite this ownership and name change, the clinic continues to provide optometry services as well as having an attached boutique store for eyewear purchases.

It is also important to note that that most programs, events, and social gatherings are hosted by religious centres in the community. These include worship and prayer gatherings, social meetings over coffee and snacks, and even farmer’s market events coordinated with local producers of fresh foods.

Table 1. Number of Services Identified and COVID-19 related status

	Number of Services (2019)	Number of Services (2022)	Open, in-person	Open with online options available	Unclear status	Closed
Education	3	3	3			
Fitness/ Recreation	3	3	3			
Food Sources	2	2	1	1		
Health/Social Services	17	18	16		2	
Housing	13	13	13			
Parks	1	1	1			
Protective Services	3	3	1	1	1	
Religious Centres	5	5	4		1	
Stores	5	5	3			2
Transportation	0	0	0			
Total	52	53	45	2	4	2

Table 2. Summary of Services COVID-19 Status and Function

Open, in-person (with modified procedures for public safety)	Open with online options available	Unclear status (with attempt to contact)	Closed
Education			
Central Public School Metropolitan College Michael G. Degroote School of Medicine			
Fitness/Recreation			
Hamilton Conservatory for the Arts Main Hess Activity Club Ryerson Recreation Centre			
Food Sources			
Big Bee Food Mart Hunter	Durand Coffee		
Health/Social Services			
Charlton Dentistry + Physiotherapy De Benetti Dentistry Professionals Advance Vision, Dr. Sheldon Salaba* G. Gall Hearing & Tinnitus Centre Guardian Pharmacy/Sutherland Pharmacy Limited Hamilton Environmental Health/City of Hamilton Healthy and Safe Communities Department, Public Health Division Hamilton Ontario Works Employment/City of Hamilton Placement Services Medical Arts Clinic Shoppers Drugmart Pharmacy Southwest Family Health Centre St. Joseph Hospital The Career Foundation Urban Healing Studio YMCA Hamilton-Seniors Active Living Centres Downtown Main Dental Office Baldan Periodontics			

Open, in-person (with modified procedures for public safety)	Open with online options available	Unclear status (with attempt to contact)	Closed
Housing			
Bay 100 Apartments Bold Towers City Housing Core Lofts Durand Retirement Residency Durand Village El Duque Apartments Fontainebleau Apartments Indwell – Caroline Apartments Jackson Villa Apartments Le Palais and Capital Terrace Lido Tower Apartments – Skyline Living Royal Place			
Parks			
Durand Park			
Protective Services			
Bates Law, Barristers & Solicitors	Derek Wilson Personal Injury Law	Alisa Family Law – Alisa P. Williams	
Religious Centres			
Central Presbyterian Church First Hamilton Christian Reformed Church MacNab Street Presbyterian Church St. Paul’s Presbyterian Church			
		St. James Church	

Open, in-person (with modified procedures for public safety)	Open with online options available	Unclear status (with attempt to contact)	Closed
Stores			Country Style
Daisy Mart Kiki's Closets Shoppers Drugmart			TD Canada Trust Branch and ATM**

*Advance Vision was previously operated under the ownership of Dr. Brian Paul and was referred to as Dr. Brian Paul's Optometry Clinic.

** TD Canada Trust Branch and ATM (Durand location) is temporarily closed however it is unclear the duration of this closure.

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Siddiqui S., Nadarajah A.. on behalf of the EMBOLDEN research team (2023). Environmental scan: Durand.URL: <https://emboldenstudy.mcmaster.ca/projects-results/>

Durand | CT 0038.00

Based on 2021 Census Data

CT Highlights

Population
= 4,172

Number of Homes
= 2,931

Population Density
= 12,540/Km²

5-year Population change = 6.6%

Age Distribution by Gender

\$39,120
Average Income
(after tax)

11.5%
Unemployment Rate

Citizenship & Immigrant Population

Canadian Citizens

Immigrants Recent Immigrants

Language Spoken at Home

English | 82.3%
 Non-official Languages | 12.8%

Highest Certificate, Diploma or Degree

No certificate, diploma or degree
 Secondary (high) school diploma or equivalency
 Postsecondary certificate, diploma or degree

Neighbourhood Homes

\$1,510 (own)
 \$1,087 (rent)

Average monthly shelter costs

82%

Rent their home

\$538,000

Average home value

69%

Apartment ≥ 5 stories

77%

Built before 1980

8%

Major repair needed

Public Health Agency of Canada
 Agence de la santé publique du Canada

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Data Source Statistics Canada. 20215370038.00 [Census tract].
www.statcan.gc.ca

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 Infographic: Neighbourhood Profile
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